
Digital Reading Habits Of Engineering College Students In Sangli District: A Case Study

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Abstract:

The rapid growth of information and communication technology has transformed reading habits traditional print-based formats to digital platforms such as smartphones, laptops tablets and e-resources. This study investigates the digital reading habits of engineering college students in Sangli district, Maharashtra. This study focused on the awareness, purpose and satisfaction with digital reading. Case study research design method used and questionnaire in Google form prepared for the data collection. This questionnaire send to 500 student randomly and 225 students was response this questionnaire. Descriptive statistics used for the analyzing the collected the data. Findings of this study the majority of the student's primary use smartphones for digital reading and main purpose of digital reading are academic performance and exam preparation. Overall students agreed that the digital reading is more convenient, time saving and quick access to information compared to print materials. The study concluded that digital resources have become mainstream in engineering education and students are largely satisfy with their digital reading. Researcher suggest that librarians and educators enhance digital literacy by organize training and awareness programme for students.

Keywords: Digital Reading, Habits, Case study, Satisfy, Engineering student, Sangli District.

Introduction:

In the 21st century the act of reading has evolved significantly. No longer has time confined to printed pages, reading increasingly takes place on digital devices such as computers. Tablets, smartphones, and e-reader usher in a new paradigm known as digital reading.(EBSCO). Digital reading has become an integral part of academic, professional and personal life. Library adopted various information and communication technology so traditional print based is increasingly being replaced or supplemented by digital formats such as e-books, e-journals, digital libraries, library blogs and mobile based technology i.e.

mobile app, social networking sites .Digital reading has a great impact on college students reading habits, there are many problems in the process of digital reading such as lack of deep thinking, weak critical consciousness and sense of innovation, which objectively shows that it is essentially a kind of “ Shallow Reading”.(CHEN, 2019)

Engineering students highly depend upon the digital tools for academic purposes due to technical curriculum and exposure to emerging technology. Engineering students are not only expected to study but also create Innovate and Design. For these purposes students' needs strong foundation, critical

thinking skills and reliable sources of information. Indian higher education has quickly shifted from print reading to digital reading on technology like laptops, tablets, smartphones and e-readers. National Digital Library and SWAYAM./NPTEL government backed initiatives have scaled access to textbooks, lectures and courseware for engineering learners nationwide, thereby normalizing digital engagement. Digital readings are very important to engineering students.

In this study, engineering students in Sangli district will have their digital reading habits examined. Reading habits changed as a Digital reading habit in engineering and technology sectors. In Pandemic year the

library was closed for staff and students. At that time many universities adapted the e-learning / online education system for colleges. After covid-19 some publishers provided free online text books for engineering students, for example Cambridge University.

Digital History refers to historians' use of modern computer and communication technologies to digitize archival materials and make them available to anyone with internet access. (Vivek, 2019). The history of digital reading started with a groundbreaking concept: the immediate distribution of books worldwide, eliminating the need for printing presses, shipping expenses and storage issues.

History of Digital Reading Habits (Bartram,(2014))

Various e-resources are easily available for students in using different kinds of technologies. All students want to read digital material for study so digital reading habits are increased.

Benefits of the Digital reading:

1. Flexibility and Adaptability
2. Easy to access and easy to sharing
3. Portability carrying more books on the one device.
4. Sustainability and environment friendly
5. Less capacity and high storage.

6. Convenience Instant access and cloud backup
7. Interactive learning.

Review of Literature:

Jeffrey (2011) conducted a case study design among four higher education institutions to explore the obstacles and support required by students in developing digital information literacy. The study emphasized that developing digital competence involves more than mere exposure to technology and it requires structured skill-building strategies. Researchers also find out the several barriers that hinder this process, including the socioeconomic limitation, gender disparities, age difference and resistance to adopting new technologies. They suggested that collaborative learning through social media platforms can serve as an effective approach to overcome these challenges.

CHEN (2019) studied the digital reading habits of college students and countermeasures of university libraries. Researchers explain that digital reading has a great impact on college students' reading habits, there are many problems in the process of digital reading such as lack of deep thinking, weak critical consciousness and sense of innovation, which objectively shows that it is essentially a kind of "shallow reading". They suggest that we need to give play to the guiding role of the library to improve the reading level and reading literacy of college students.

Vivek, & Dr. Sivadasan (2019) book entitled Digital History HIS 4C03. Understanding the Digital History, preserving the past, Tools of Digital history, Digital divide and Open access & copyright all the content explained in this book. The author explains that digital history refers to historians' use of modern computer and

communication technologies to digitize archival materials and make them available to anyone with internet access.

Subaveerapandiyan and Sinha (2021) conducted a survey study on the reading habits and digital literacy of the central university Tamilnadu students. Researchers found that the majority of the students are well known about digital tools and usage, and most of the students are excellent in digital literacy skills. They conclude that Digital and media literacy is one of the ways to reach the paperless society and library because when one person is educated, they know how to access the technology and use the technology.

Objectives of the Studies:

1. To find out awareness of digital reading materials.
2. To find out the purpose of digital readings.
3. To find out students are satisfy with digits reading habits

Research Methodology:

The case study method is a very important & popular form of qualitative analysis and involves a careful and complete observation of social units. (Kothari, 2011). A case study research design used for this study. The quantitative survey method used for collecting primary data.

Population and Sample:

The population of the study selected undergraduate engineering students enrolled in various engineering colleges in Sangli district, Maharashtra. A sample of size 500 students randomly selected for this study.

Data Collection Tools:

The structured questionnaire prepared in google form for data collection. The questionnaire divide in the four section:

- Section I:- Demographic information about student
- Section II :- Awareness of digital reading habits
- Section II :- Purpose of the digital reading
- Section IV:- Overall Satisfaction of digital reading.

The questionnaire is sent to 500 students using the email, whatsapp number as well as through institution heads. Out of 500 students there are 225 students who responded to the questionnaire.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

After collecting data through Google form, data compiled automatically in Google form. Data exported to excel format for tabulation. Descriptive statistics used for the analysis of frequency and percentage of the data.

Section I Demographic:**Table 1: Demographic Frequency Distribution of Respondents**

Type	Division	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	148	65.8%
	Female	77	34.2%
Age	Under 18	21	9.3%
	18-22	189	84%
	23-25	10	4.4%
	26-30	5	2.2%
Academic Year	First	5	2.2%
	Second	139	61%
	Third	62	27.6%
	Fourth	15	6.7%
	Graduate	4	1.8%

Table 1 shows the demographic frequency distribution of respondents. Out of 225 respondents, the major response was 148(65.8%) male, while 77(34.2%) female respondents. This indicates that the majority of respondents is male. The age profile shows

that the majority of responses was younger. 189(84%) respondents were between the ages of 18-22 years old. Academic year distribution shows that the majority of respondents in 139 (61%) second year.

Section II Awareness of Digital Reading Habits:**Fig 1. Awareness of digital reading Habits.**

Fig. 1 shows that the 199 (88.8%) respondent was aware from the digital reading and 26 (11.6%) respondent was not aware from digital reading.

Frequency of Engage on Digital Reading

Fig. 2: Frequency of engaging in digital reading.

Fig. 2 shows that 75(33%) students engaged in several time for digital reading, 72(32%) students spend time in daily on digital reading.

Device used for the digital reading

Fig 3 :Devices used for Digital Reading

Fig. 3 shows that, 193(85.8%) Smartphones mostly used devices and easy access drives for digital reading. 59 (26.2%) Laptop is the

second option device used for the mostly academic purpose. Another device such as Tablet and computer is used rarely for digital reading.

Section III Purpose of Digital Reading:

Purpose of Digital Reading Habits

Fig. 4 Purpose of Digital Reading

Fig. 4 shows that the Academic (50.2%) and Exam preparation (46.2%) is the first purpose of digital reading. Notes and

Assignment/Project are significant purpose of digital reading.

Fig 5: Use for staying updates engineering trends

Fig. 5 shows that most of the students 99(44%) regularly use digital material for updating the engineering trends. Some of the students 61(27%) occasionally as well as

50(22%) rarely use digital material for updating for new trends in engineering. 7% of students do not use digital material for the updating of new trends in engineering.

Section IV: Satisfaction of Digital reading

Digital Material Vs Printing Material (Convenient)

Fig. 6 Digital Material Vs Printing Material (Convenient)

Fig. 6 shows that most of the students strongly agree that digital reading is more convenient than printing material. Some

students are neutral about this and 16% and 17% students strongly disagree and agree respectively.

Digital reading save time & Quick access

Fig. 7 Digital reading saves time and Quick Access

Fig. 7 shows that 36% of students strongly agree that digital reading saves time and information is easily accessible anywhere

and anytime. Only 6% and 8% of students strongly disagree and disagree with respectively.

Fig.8: Overall Satisfaction of digital reading.

Fig. 8 shows that 50% of students are happy with digital reading. A small portion of students are neutral, disagree with digital reading.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that the students mostly used smartphones for digital reading, so that shows the mobile first learning process. The main purpose of the digital reading is academic performance as well as exam preparation. Most of the students use digital material for staying updated on engineering trends, while some engage occasionally. The majority of students strongly agree that digital reading is more convenient, time saving and easily accessible information anywhere, anytime. But some of the students prepare print material for concentration and comfort. For all the findings, researchers concluded that the students are satisfied with their digital reading, indicating that digital resources are mainstream in engineering education.

It is suggested that librarians arrange training programmes and awareness

programmes for students to improve skills in digital resources. Orientation programs and webinar can help students become aware of NPTEL, NDL SWAYAM government initiatives which provide authentic learning.

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